

HERITAGE OF GLUTEN CONTENT IN SPRING SOFT WHEAT HYBRIDS

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Summary. Studying the type of inheritance of gluten, which is a reliable marker in determining the quality of wheat grain, is a factor in controlling its stable quality. In hybrid combinations, the type of inheritance of gluten is controlled under the influence of polymer genes, and the phenotypic separation is 1:4:6:4:1 in F_2 .

Key words: wheat, X^2 , genetic analysis, hybrid combination, gluten, separation.

Gluten is of great importance in the baking industry, determining such dough characteristics as elasticity, elasticity when mixed with water and serves as one of the criteria for determining the quality of flour. In the milling industry, this indicator is added to low quality flour to obtain flour that meets the requirements of the standard. The use of dry gluten allows you to increase the absorption of water during dough kneading, extending the shelf life of products, improving the structure and porosity and increasing the specific volume of bread (3).

1-table.

Statistical analysis of the heritability of gluten content in hybrids of spring soft wheat, X^2 .

Information	Amount of gluten, %					Σ
	1- class 32<	2- class 32-28	3- class 28-23	4- class 23-18	5- class 18 >	
The result obtained in the experiment, x	8	80	44	54	14	200
Expected result, q'	12,5	75	50	50	12,5	200
Expected ratio, q	1	6	4	4	1	16
Deviation, d $d=(x-q')$	-4,5	5	-6	4	1,5	-

Deviation area, d^2	20,25	25	36	16	2,25	-
$\frac{d^2}{q'}$	1,62	0,33	0,72	0,32	0,18	3,17
$\chi^2 = \Sigma d^2/q'$	3,17					

P=0,05

It was revealed that in the studied hybrids of spring wheat, the content of protein, gluten and sedimentation index have different types of inheritance, when splitting generations, the main share is occupied by combinations with positive dominance and intermediate inheritance. The gluten index in soft spring wheat hybrids is a fairly reliable marker (2).

In order to study the heritability of grain (1) quality indicators of spring soft wheat, a genetic analysis (method X^2) was carried out for the heritability of midori gluten in hybrids (Table 1).

The results show (table №. 1) 1.62 to class 1 (dominant-A1A1A2A2); 0.33 to class 2 (interval A1A1A2a2); 0.72 to grade 3 (medium-A1A1a2a2); 0.32 to grade 4 (medium-A1a1a2a2); Data for phenotypes with a marker of 0.18 (recessive-a1a1a2a2) were obtained for class 5. Their sum was 3.17. The probability of coincidence of the experimental result with the theoretical one is the following, the degree of freedom (n the number of phenotypic groups (5) is equal to -1=4). With a probability $p=0.05$, the comparison number in the Fisher table with a degree of freedom of 4 is 9.488 (Table 2).

2-table

Determination of the X^2 value at various degrees of freedom.

Fisher chart:

Degree of freedom, n	P						
	0,99	0,95	0,80	0,50	0,10	0,05	0,01
1.	0,0001	0,0393	0,642	0,455	1,642	3,841	6,635
2.	0,101	0,103	0,446	1,386	3,219	5,991	9,210
3.	0,115	0,352	1,005	2,366	4,642	7,815	11,34
4.	0,297	0,71	1,649	3,357	5,989	9,488	13,27
5.	0,554	1,145	2,343	4,351	7,289	11,070	15,08
6.	0,872	1,635	3,070	5,348	8,558	12,592	16,81

7.	1,239	2,167	3,822	6,346	9,803	14,067	18,47
8.	1,646	2,733	4,594	7,344	11,030	15,507	20,09
9.	2,088	3,25	5,380	8,348	12,242	16,919	21,66
10.	2,558	3,940	6,179	9,342	13,442	18,307	23,20

The amount of X^2 determined from the results of the experiment is 3.17, according to the null hypothesis $3.17 < 9.488$, which means there is no difference between the result obtained in the experiment and the theoretically expected result. According to the results of the analysis, the inheritance of genes that determine the amount of gluten in F_2 hybrids is inherited under the influence of additive genes, and the phenotypic ratio corresponds to 1:4:6:4:1.

In conclusion, a statistical analysis of the inheritance by the X^2 method of other grain quality tests, including protein content, sedimentation index, and glassiness indices in hybrids, showed that the inheritance of these traits is controlled by additive genes ($n < 9,488$). This indicates a high correlation between the recorded indicators.

References.

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